

A muscle-specific allelic imbalance in *IARS1* unmasks a novel compound heterozygous mechanism in congenital myopathy

Adrien Rihoux^{1,2}, Clémence Gonthier-Cummings^{1,2}, Jennifer Hauteclouque^{1,2}, Alexie Gagné^{1,2}, Laura K. Hamilton², Jason Karamchandani^{3,4}, Audrey Labarre², Alex Parker^{1,2}, Bernard Brais⁵, Martine Tétreault^{1,2}

¹ Univ. of Montreal, Montreal, QC, Canada, ² CRCHUM, Montreal, QC, Canada, ³ Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Montreal Neurological Institute, Montreal, QC, Canada, ⁴ Department of Pathology, Montreal Neurological Institute, Montreal, QC, Canada, ⁵ Montreal Neurological Institute and Hospital, Montreal, QC, Canada

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Background

We investigated a non-consanguineous family with **congenital myopathy**: unaffected parents; **all siblings affected** (two males, one female) with early hypotonia, gait difficulty, distal laxity/contractures, and scoliosis. **Muscle biopsy** shows fiber atrophy with central nuclei and mild fibrosis. **Genetic analysis** identified a maternal *IARS1* missense (c.1982G>A, p.R661H) and a paternal deep-intronic change. *IARS1* encodes the cytosolic isoleucyl-tRNA synthetase (IleRS), which charges tRNA^{Ile} and functions within the multi-tRNA-synthetase complex. **Muscle RNA-seq** shows **allelic imbalance**: the paternal allele contributes ~10% of transcripts while the maternal missense accounts for ~90%; in matched fibroblasts, allelic expression is balanced.

Hypothesis: Muscle-specific down-regulation of the paternal allele forces predominant expression of the maternal missense, pushing *IARS1* activity below the level required for myogenic remodeling and maintenance.

Figure 1: Muscle RNA-seq: Maternal ~90% • Paternal ~10% (allelic imbalance of *IARS1*).

Figure 2: Fibroblast DNA-seq: Maternal ~50% • Paternal ~50% (balanced expression).

Objectives

- C. elegans – sarcomere integrity**: Test whether reducing *iars-1* (RNAi) disrupts sarcomere organization, benchmarked to OP50 (negative control) and *unc-89* (positive control).
- Metabolic activity (WST-1)**: Measure whether fibroblast to pseudo-myoblast conversion induces the expected metabolic down-shift; compare matched patient lines with controls, with myoblast baselines (NEC/EC and KO-IARS).
- Proliferation (Incucyte)**: Quantify growth dynamics before and after conversion (doubling time) and assess the magnitude of patient–control differences.

Muscle structure assay

Experimental design

Perturbation: reduce *iars-1* activity by feeding RNAi in young adults.

Preparation & imaging: animals mounted at Day 1/3/5; body-wall muscle visualized under fluorescence to assess sarcomeric organization.

Scoring: High / Medium / Low

Lowering *iars-1* progressively disrupts sarcomeres

Design & readout. Synchronized young adults on OP50 (negative control), *iars-1* (RNAi) (experimental), or *unc-89* (positive control). Top panels illustrate **Low / Medium / High** organization; bottom stacked bars = **number of animals per category** at Day 1, 3, 5.

Result. Relative to OP50, *iars-1* (RNAi) shows a **time-dependent shift** toward Medium/High by Day 5.

Metabolic activity

Experimental design

Assay setup: patient fibroblasts and **MyoD-driven transdifferentiation** cells seeded at uniform density in 96-well plates; add **WST-1**, incubate at 37°C, and read **450 nm** with **650 nm** reference on a plate reader. Slope measured in the linear phase.

Myogenic conversion triggers a metabolic shift in controls; patients show incomplete reprogramming.

Readout. Baseline myoblasts (NEC, EC, KO-IARS) are indistinguishable. During fibroblast to pseudo-myoblast conversion, all controls decrease, whereas patients show no decrease. Patient–control differences are small in fibroblasts (blue) but widen after conversion (orange), indicating failure of metabolic reprogramming in patient

Proliferation

Experiment design

Acquisition: standardized seeding density; phase-contrast images acquired automatically every 3 h for 5 days in an Incucyte system.

Outputs: growth curves per well; **doubling time** computed from the exponential growth window.

Myogenic conversion shortens doubling time and enlarges patient–control gaps.

Readout. Across donors, pseudo-myoblasts divide faster than matched fibroblasts, confirming a conversion linked acceleration of growth. In paired comparisons, patient–control differences are present at the fibroblast stage and increase after conversion, indicating divergent growth trajectories post-reprogramming.

Conclusion

Muscle-specific *IARS1* imbalance (paternal silencing + p.R661H) drives a dose-sensitive myopathy. *iars-1* reduction disrupts sarcomeres in worms; in patient cells, myogenic conversion fails the normal metabolic down-shift and amplifies a baseline proliferation gap, producing divergent post-conversion growth trajectories, a muscle-restricted remodeling defect.

Future perspective

Mechanism: long-read isoforms, allele-specific expression, methylation.

Rescue: paternal-allele reactivation and isoleucine; success = restored down-shift and differentiation.

Fundings

